

Imagery Intelligence in Contemporary Counterterrorism: A Comparative Study of Nigeria and Somalia

**Faseke, Babajimi O., PhD & †Adeoye, Bisola O.*

Abstract

The study examines the use of imagery intelligence (IMINT) in counterterrorism operations against Boko Haram in Nigeria and Al-Shabaab in Somalia. Despite years of sustained military campaigns, both insurgent groups have remained resilient, continuing to operate in difficult terrains as well as exploiting intelligence gaps within state security structures. While modern militaries increasingly possess advanced surveillance technologies, the practical role and effectiveness of imagery-based intelligence in counterterrorism operations in Africa remain insufficiently examined. It is against this backdrop that the study investigates how IMINT contributes counterterrorism strategies in both Nigeria and Somalia. Situating IMINT within the broader framework of Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT), the paper adopts a qualitative and descriptive approach based on a review of relevant scholarly literature and documented operational experiences from Nigeria and Somalia. The analysis suggests that IMINT has enhanced the ability of security forces to identify militant camps, track movements, and support military operations against insurgent groups. However, its effectiveness depends largely on enhancing institutional capacity, inter-agency coordination, and its integration with other intelligence fields. The paper concludes that while IMINT alone cannot defeat insurgent movements, it remains an increasingly valuable component of contemporary counterterrorism strategy when integrated within a broader intelligence architecture.

Keywords: imagery intelligence (IMINT), geospatial intelligence (GEOINT), Boko Haram, Al-Shabaab, counterterrorism strategy

* Dept. of History & International Studies, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria. bfaseke@gmail.com; bo.faseke@acu.edu.ng.

† Dept. of History & International Studies, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria. adeoyebisola827@gmail.com

Introduction

Since the turn of the twenty-first century, the African continent has gained an unwanted attention for being one of the hotbeds of terrorism and insurgency globally (Falode & Faseke, 2023). This is particularly the case in West Africa where Boko Haram and ISWAP are active as well in East Africa where Al-Shabaab is dominant. The U.K Guardian reports that since 2009 Boko Haram and its splinter group, ISWAP have been responsible for the death of over 40,000 people (Egbejule, 2025). Similarly, 20,000 people have been killed in Somalia since 2006 (Council on Foreign Relations, 2025). Onapajo et al. (2012), Faseke (2013), Animasawun & Saka (2013), Voll (2015) and Falode (2016) have all dissected different aspects of Boko Haram motives and operations, while Marchal (2009), Shinn (2011), Petrich (2019) and Kheyre (2022) have done the same for Al-Shabaab. The authors concluded that apart from the killings, the insurgencies of Boko Haram in Nigeria and Al-Shabaab in Somalia have caused severe humanitarian and security crises. Both groups have displaced millions and destroyed communities. The targeted attacks on educational institutions, commercial centers, and critical infrastructure have undermined governance, disrupted economic activities, and exacerbated poverty, thereby impeding development and political stability in the affected regions.

With such monstrous atrocities, municipal governments and international organisations have sought different counterterrorism mechanisms to arrest the threats of Boko Haram and Al-Shabaab. These measures have largely been dependent on the ground forces of the military, with scholars examining various dimensions these military combats have taken (Agbibo, 2015; Oriola, 2021; Akinbile et al., 2025). But army operations against insurgents can only achieve limited results without the supportive role intelligence operations play. Indeed, timely intelligence is crucial in assisting the army to combat insurgency because it enables security forces to identify insurgent networks, locate hideouts and supply routes, anticipate planned attacks, understand local support structures,

and deploy troops strategically, thereby reducing operational uncertainty, improving the effectiveness of military operations, and minimizing casualties among both soldiers and civilians (Amaraegbu, 2013; Nte, 2013; Lasisi & Ene, 2019; Falode & Faseke, 2023).

Of the different kinds of intelligence, Imagery intelligence (IMINT) has a special place in modern counterintelligence because it helps provide visual evidence that can corroborate or challenge information gathered through other forms of intelligence (Lowenthal, 2017; Johnson, 2010). Yet scant attention has been paid to how IMINT affects counterinsurgency strategies in the fight against both Boko Haram and Al-Shabaab. This study bridges the gap in this regard by not only identifying how IMINT has been deployed as a counterinsurgency mechanism in both countries, but also drawing a comparative analysis between both cases. The rest of the study is divided into four sections. It begins with a methodological section that outlines the research design, sources of data, and analytical approach adopted for the study. This is followed by a conceptual discussion of intelligence and its various forms, paying particular attention to the place of IMINT within the broader field of Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT). The subsequent sections examine the application of imagery intelligence in Nigeria's campaign against Boko Haram and in Somalia's counterterrorism operations against Al-Shabaab. A comparative section then evaluates the similarities and differences in the deployment of IMINT in the two contexts, highlighting variations in operational environments, technological capacity, and international support.

Methodology

The approach to this study is primarily descriptive and analytical, relying on documentary evidence and secondary data to assess how imagery-based intelligence has influenced military operations and counterinsurgency outcomes in the two cases. A comparative case-

study framework was selected because it allows the researcher to explore similarities and differences in the deployment of IMINT across two distinct operational environments while identifying broader patterns in intelligence-driven counterterrorism. Nigeria and Somalia were selected because both countries face persistent insurgencies but differ significantly in technological capacity, international support, and terrain. Comparing the two contexts makes it possible to identify how variations in resources, institutional capacity, and international cooperation influence the effectiveness of imagery intelligence in counterterrorism.

Data for the study were derived mainly from secondary sources, including scholarly journal articles, academic books, policy reports, and credible media publications on intelligence studies, counterterrorism, and African security. Additional information was obtained from institutional publications and security reports produced by organizations such as the Council on Foreign Relations and reputable international news outlets. These materials help understand the operational use of aerial surveillance, drones, satellite imagery, and other visual intelligence tools in counterterrorism operations. The collected data were analysed using qualitative content analysis. Relevant texts were carefully examined to identify recurring themes relating to the use of imagery intelligence, including surveillance capabilities, operational coordination, leadership targeting, troop deployment, and challenges associated with imagery interpretation. Through systematic coding and thematic grouping, the study traced how IMINT contributed to military planning and operational effectiveness in both Nigeria and Somalia. Particular attention was paid to documented instances where aerial or satellite imagery played a role in detecting insurgent camps, tracking militant movements, or enabling precision strikes.

Finally, the study acknowledges certain methodological limitations. Because of the sensitive nature of intelligence operations, much of the available information is derived from

publicly accessible sources rather than classified materials. This inevitably constrains the level of operational detail that can be analysed. Nevertheless, by triangulating evidence from multiple scholarly and policy sources, the research provides a credible and analytically grounded assessment of the role of imagery intelligence in contemporary counterterrorism strategies in Africa.

Conceptualizing Intelligence and the Place of IMINT

There is no universally acceptable definition of intelligence. What tends to unite most interpretations, however, is a common understanding of its purpose. In essence, intelligence exists to provide an advantage over an adversary by reducing uncertainty and strengthening security. As Jensen, McElreath, and Graves (2013) explain, intelligence provides decision-makers a crucial strategic advantage that allows them to act with knowledge that their competitors or opponents may not possess. In this sense, the ultimate value of intelligence lies in its capacity to produce a decision advantage. Efforts to define the concept more precisely have also been undertaken in the literature. Through qualitative and quantitative analysis of numerous definitions, Dokman (2019) identifies about fifteen key elements that frequently appear in discussions of intelligence. Among these are information, collection, analysis, threats, objectives, foreign actors, and the presence of an end-user who can act upon the intelligence provided. Falode (2021) offers a robust definition that accommodates these elements, by defining the concept as ‘the process of collection, collation, analysis, interpretation and conversion of raw data into actionable information by a state with the aim of ensuring its relative security.’

However, intelligence does vary depending on channel and purpose. According to the Interagency OPSEC Support Staff (IOSS, 2023), intelligence agencies generally obtain raw data from five principal sources. One of these is human intelligence (HUMINT), which relies on information gathered directly from human

informants or operatives. Another is signals intelligence (SIGINT), which is concerned with intercepting and analysing electronic communications and signals. Measurement and Signatures Intelligence (MASINT) involves the technical examination of scientific indicators, including those associated with nuclear or biological weapons. In addition, financial intelligence (FININT) focuses on analyzing financial transactions to uncover suspicious patterns or connections linked to illegal activities. Finally, geospatial intelligence (GEOINT) encompasses the interpretation of imagery, maps, and other location-based data, and it also serves as the broader field that includes imagery intelligence (IMINT) (Faseke, 2022).

Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT) is a broad intelligence field that integrates geographical information such as maps, terrain data, satellite imagery, and geographic information systems in order to analyze activities tied to specific locations. Within this broader field, we have Imagery Intelligence (IMINT), which focuses more specifically on the interpretation of visual images obtained from satellites, reconnaissance aircraft, or unmanned aerial systems. Scholars note that while GEOINT combines several spatial datasets, IMINT concentrates primarily on extracting meaning from images themselves (Lowenthal, 2017; Jensen, McElreath & Graves, 2013). In the context of this study, this distinction is particularly relevant. Boko Haram and Al-Shabaab operate in remote and difficult terrains that make it difficult to detect their location and operations. Consequently, imagery analysis is important to counterterrorism since it can reveal training camps, movements, settlements, and logistics. IMINT, therefore, provides concrete visual evidence that aids the assessment and strategic planning against insurgent groups (Lowenthal, 2017; Johnson, 2010).

Imagery Intelligence against Boko Haram in Nigeria

Nigeria's IMINT operations are handled by the air force wing of the Defence Intelligence Agency (DIA), which is Nigeria's premier military intelligence agency, established in 1986 to provide actionable, strategic intelligence to the Armed Forces and Ministry of Defence. IMINT has been a vital tool in Nigeria's fight against Boko Haram, providing critical visual data that enhances the military's ability to plan, execute, and assess counterterrorism operations (Falode & Faseke, 2023). This involves the use of satellite imagery, aerial reconnaissance, and drone surveillance to gather information about Boko Haram's movements, camps, and logistical networks. This form of intelligence is especially valuable in the vast and often inaccessible regions of northeastern Nigeria, where Boko Haram operates. The use of this form of intelligence has yielded some positive results (Falode & Faseke, 2023). For instance, between 4th and 5th of 2013 air power was instrumental in the hot pursuit of BH insurgents who had just attacked Gajiram and Bullabulin Ngaura communities in Borno. The air force was able to provide air cover and IMINT to the ground troops, who pursued the terrorists to their hideouts and killed over 50 of them (Marama, 2014).

IMINT has also been instrumental in monitoring the movements of Boko Haram fighters, especially during their raids on villages and towns. Aerial surveillance conducted by drones and manned aircraft can track the movements of Boko Haram convoys in real-time, providing the Nigerian military with the ability to intercept these forces before they can carry out attacks. This capability has been particularly important in disrupting Boko Haram's operations, as the group often relies on the element of surprise and the cover of dense terrain to carry out its attacks. The ability to track these movements from the air has allowed the Nigerian military to preempt attacks and protect vulnerable communities (Falode & Faseke, 2023). A good example was particularly the case when on the 3rd of December 2014 the air force combined

with ground troops to successfully repel Boko Haram attack in Konduga, Borno State, killing over 200 insurgents (Oyewole, 2017). There was also the March 8 2015 experience, whereby the headquarters of Gujba LGA Buni Yadi and Buni Gari, among other communities in Yobe State, were recovered by air-supported ground formation, following two days of a series of airstrikes in an operation that killed over 200 insurgents (Vanguard, 2015). Nigeria, with the assistance of Chad and Niger, launched air and ground strikes against Boko Haram as troops recapture Buni Yadi (Vanguard, 2015). In short, the air force has been very integral in Nigeria's counterterrorism. However, its contributions have been largely combatant as opposed to the provision of intelligence per se (Vanguard, 2015).

In fact, the airspace is believed to have been underutilized in providing imagery intelligence and this has cost the SJMTF losses in their struggle against Boko Haram. There was evidence of inadequacy of air power in gathering and sharing intelligence with ground troops in the Gambororu-Ngala siege in Borno State on May 5, 2014 (Marama, 2014). The invasion had claimed 300 lives and had come shortly after troops that were supposed to guard the town were redeployed to pursue fleeing insurgents along the Lake Chad region (Marama, 2014). The same lapses could be identified in similar occurrences in Bama, Chibok, Gwoza and many other locations at different periods between 2013 and 2015 (Oyewole, 2017).

The availability of satellites and drones has significantly enhanced the provision of IMINT in Nigeria's counterterrorism efforts. In recent years, Nigeria has operated a number of satellite that can serve this purpose. For instance, there is Condor-E2, which was designed and managed exclusively for military-security use. Three others (Mohammed VI-A & B, and Tiba-1) were designed and managed for both civil and military purposes, while others (NigeriaSat-2, NigeriaEdusat-1 and Nigcomsat-1R) were designed and managed for civil purposes but significantly employed for

military use (Oyewole, 2020: 153). Apart from NigeriaSat-X and NigeriaEduSat-1 that were designed and built by Nigerians using AIT facilities in the UK and Japan, however, these satellites associated with the Nigerian military do not belong to Nigeria. Mohammed VI-A & B, and Tiba-1 were sponsored by Morocco and Egypt, while Condor-E2 was sponsored by South Africa in 2014 (Oyewole, 2020: 156). Nevertheless, some of these have been used in Nigeria's war against insurgents. For example, the Nigerian security forces relied on spy satellites and drones to collect data to trace the location of the 276 abducted schoolgirls (Tella, 2022: 5). However, these satellite sources are still underutilized in aiding IMINT (Lasisi & Ene, 2019).

In addition, international collaboration has played a key role in enhancing Nigeria's IMINT capabilities. Countries such as the United States have provided Nigeria with satellite imagery and drone support, significantly boosting the country's ability to gather and analyze visual intelligence (Falode & Faseke, 2023). The U.S. Africa Command (AFRICOM) has been particularly active in providing IMINT support to Nigeria, including the deployment of drones from bases in Niger. This partnership has not only provided Nigeria with advanced imagery but also with training and technical support to improve the country's own IMINT capabilities (Falode & Faseke, 2023).

In summary, IMINT has been a crucial component of Nigeria's counterterrorism strategy against Boko Haram. The ability to gather detailed visual intelligence has significantly enhanced the military's ability to conduct precise and effective operations, thereby disrupting Boko Haram's activities and reducing the threat it poses to national security. The success of these efforts has been greatly aided by international collaboration, which has provided Nigeria with access to advanced IMINT technologies and expertise. As Boko Haram continues to evolve and adapt, the ongoing development and application of IMINT will remain

essential to the Nigerian military's efforts to contain and ultimately defeat the group.

Barriers to Effective Imagery Intelligence in the Northeast

Deploying imagery intelligence against Boko Haram in Nigeria faces significant challenges, beginning with the region's dense and often inhospitable terrain. The northeastern part of Nigeria, where Boko Haram operates most actively has rugged landscapes, forests, and remote areas that are difficult to monitor using satellite imagery or aerial reconnaissance (Oyewole, 2020: 162). Boko Haram fighters exploit this terrain to their advantage, using natural cover to conceal their movements, camps, and logistics. For instance, the Sambisa Forest, a key Boko Haram stronghold, has proven challenging for Nigerian forces to monitor effectively due to its vastness and dense vegetation, which hinders clear imagery.

Another challenge is the group's use of mobile tactics and small, dispersed units. Boko Haram often avoids large concentrations of forces, which would be easier to detect from the air. Instead, they operate in small, mobile groups that can quickly disperse and regroup, making it difficult for IMINT to provide actionable intelligence in real-time (Oyewole, 2017). This decentralized approach complicates efforts to track and target Boko Haram's activities through imagery, as their movements are unpredictable and often occur under the cover of darkness or adverse weather conditions, further reducing the effectiveness of IMINT.

The limitations of Nigeria's domestic IMINT capabilities also pose a significant challenge. Nigeria relies heavily on international partners for advanced satellite and aerial imagery, as its own resources are limited. However, the timeliness and quality of this imagery can be affected by various factors, including the availability of satellites, cloud cover, and the priorities of international partners. This reliance on external sources means that Nigerian forces may not always have access to the most up-

to-date or high-resolution imagery, which can delay or undermine counterterrorism operations.

Additionally, the interpretation of imagery intelligence requires specialized skills and expertise, which are in short supply within Nigeria's military and intelligence agencies. The effective use of IMINT depends not just on acquiring imagery but also on the ability to analyze and interpret it accurately. A lack of trained personnel can lead to misinterpretation of data, resulting in missed opportunities or, worse, misguided operations. For example, misidentification of targets based on unclear or poorly analyzed imagery could lead to civilian casualties or the destruction of non-military infrastructure, which can fuel local resentment and play into Boko Haram's narrative (Oyewole, 2017: 224).

Finally, Boko Haram's use of deception and camouflage techniques further complicates the deployment of IMINT. The group has become adept at hiding its activities from aerial and satellite surveillance by using natural and artificial camouflage, as well as by operating in close proximity to civilian populations. This deliberate blending with civilians makes it difficult to distinguish between legitimate targets and non-combatants, posing ethical and operational challenges for forces relying on imagery intelligence. As a result, IMINT alone is often insufficient for actionable intelligence and must be supplemented by other forms of intelligence, such as human intelligence or signals intelligence, to achieve effective results in counterterrorism operations against Boko Haram (Oyewole, 2017).

Imagery Intelligence in Somalia's Counterterrorism Operations

Unlike in Nigeria, the success of IMINT in Somalia's counterterrorism efforts has been largely dependent on international collaboration, particularly with the United States and other Western allies. AFRICOM has been a key player in providing IMINT support to Somali forces, supplying advanced drone technology, satellite

imagery, and analytical expertise. This collaboration has extended to sharing intelligence with the African Union Mission in Somalia (AMISOM) and Somali national forces, ensuring a coordinated and comprehensive approach to counterterrorism. For instance, the deployment of MQ-9 Reaper drones by AFRICOM has provided continuous surveillance over al-Shabaab territories, enabling constant monitoring and rapid response to emerging threats (Meservey, 2019: 74). This international support has been crucial in augmenting Somalia's limited IMINT capabilities, allowing for a more sustained and effective campaign against al-Shabaab.

While Somalia was not directly involved in deploying IMINT against Al-Shabaab, IMINT has been a crucial component of the counterterrorism operations in Somalia, providing actionable intelligence that has significantly enhanced the effectiveness of military and security operations. IMINT involves the use of satellite imagery, aerial reconnaissance, and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs or drones) to gather visual data on al-Shabaab's movements, camps, and operational infrastructure. Given Somalia's challenging terrain and the dispersed nature of al-Shabaab's operations, IMINT has proven invaluable in overcoming the limitations of ground-based intelligence, enabling Somali and international forces to monitor and respond to threats more effectively. The integration of IMINT into Somalia's broader intelligence framework has allowed for more precise targeting, reduced collateral damage, and improved the overall coordination of counterterrorism efforts (Meservey, 2019).

One of the primary use of IMINT against al-Shabaab has been in the identification and targeting of the group's leadership and key infrastructure. Al-Shabaab operates in remote areas of southern Somalia, often in regions that are difficult to access by ground forces. Through the use of satellite imagery and drone surveillance, intelligence agencies have been able to locate and monitor al-Shabaab's command centers, training camps, and weapons depots. This visual intelligence has enabled precise

airstrikes and special operations, particularly those conducted by the United States Africa Command (AFRICOM) in collaboration with Somali forces. For example, IMINT was instrumental in the targeted killing of senior al-Shabaab leaders such as Ahmed Abdi Godane, the group's emir, in 2014 (ABC News, 2014). By pinpointing the exact locations of high-value targets, IMINT has played a pivotal role in disrupting al-Shabaab's command and control structure, significantly weakening the group's operational capabilities.

IMINT has also been crucial in monitoring the movements of al-Shabaab fighters, particularly as they conduct raids, move between safe houses, or attempt to evade military pressure. UAVs have been extensively used to track convoys of al-Shabaab militants, providing real-time intelligence to Somali and international forces. This capability has allowed for the interception of al-Shabaab units before they can carry out attacks or relocate to more secure areas. For instance, drone surveillance has been used to follow al-Shabaab movements across the porous border between Somalia and Kenya, where the group frequently launches cross-border attacks. The ability to observe these movements from the air has given Somali and allied forces a significant tactical advantage, enabling them to preempt al-Shabaab's operations and reduce the group's ability to project power beyond its strongholds (Falode & Faseke, 2023).

Somalia's underdeveloped infrastructure and limited technological capabilities pose challenges in fully utilizing the data gathered through IMINT. While international partners provide much of the imagery and analysis, the Somali forces often struggle to effectively integrate this intelligence into their operations due to a lack of training and resources. These challenges underscore the need for ongoing capacity-building efforts to enhance Somalia's ability to independently leverage IMINT in its counterterrorism strategy (Falode & Faseke, 2023).

Limitations of Imagery Intelligence in the Somali Theatre

Imagery intelligence (IMINT) against Al-Shabaab in Somalia is challenged by the country's vast and varied terrain, which includes deserts, forests, and remote, rural areas. These landscapes provide natural cover for Al-Shabaab's operations, making it difficult for satellites or aerial reconnaissance to identify and monitor the group's activities. For instance, the dense forests in southern Somalia, such as those in the Juba region, offer concealment for training camps and weapons caches, complicating efforts to gather actionable intelligence through imagery. Additionally, the frequent cloud cover in some areas can obscure satellite imagery, further reducing the effectiveness of IMINT in providing timely and accurate information (Ingiriis, 2020: 140).

Another challenge is Al-Shabaab's use of mobile and decentralized tactics, which complicates efforts to track and target their movements through IMINT. The group often avoids large formations and instead operates in small, mobile units that can quickly disperse and regroup. This makes it difficult for aerial or satellite imagery to capture significant concentrations of fighters or equipment that could be used to plan strikes. For example, after attacks, Al-Shabaab militants are known to blend back into civilian populations or relocate to new areas, evading detection by IMINT assets (Ingiriis, 2020).

The limitations of Somalia's infrastructure also hinder effective IMINT deployment. The country's lack of developed roads and transportation networks means that many areas where Al-Shabaab operates are difficult to access and monitor. This lack of infrastructure not only limits the ability to deploy drones or aircraft for sustained surveillance but also hinders the quick deployment of ground forces to verify or act on imagery intelligence. Additionally, the scarcity of reliable communication networks in remote areas can delay the transmission of imagery data, reducing its usefulness in real-time operations (Shortland, 2012).

Interpreting imagery intelligence in Somalia is also particularly

challenging due to the group's adept use of deception and camouflage techniques. Al-Shabaab militants often hide in plain sight, using civilian infrastructure or natural cover to avoid detection. For instance, the group has been known to construct tunnels, use underground bunkers, or hide weapons and fighters within civilian buildings, making it difficult for IMINT to distinguish between legitimate targets and non-combatants. These tactics increase the risk of collateral damage, which can undermine the effectiveness of counterterrorism operations and lead to significant political and social backlash (Kheyre, 2022).

Finally, the reliance on international partners for advanced IMINT capabilities introduces challenges related to coordination and timely access to intelligence. Somalia lacks the domestic capacity to operate high-tech IMINT platforms like drones or advanced satellites, relying instead on support from international allies such as the United States or the African Union mission in Somalia (AMISOM) (Shortland, 2012). However, differences in priorities, bureaucratic delays, and the need for approval from multiple stakeholders can result in delays or gaps in intelligence sharing. These delays can diminish the effectiveness of IMINT, as actionable intelligence may arrive too late to be of use in dynamic operational environments where Al-Shabaab can rapidly change tactics or locations.

Contrasting the Use of Imagery Intelligence in Nigeria and Somalia

Imagery Intelligence (IMINT) has become an essential component of counterterrorism strategies in both Nigeria and Somalia, where it plays a significant role in combating Boko Haram and Al-Shabaab, respectively. However, the implementation, effectiveness, and challenges of IMINT in these two contexts differ due to variations in terrain, technological capabilities, international support, and the operational tactics of the terrorist groups involved.

One of the key differences in the use of IMINT in Nigeria

and Somalia lies in the level of technological capability and international support available. In Nigeria, IMINT has been significantly bolstered by international partnerships, particularly with the United States and France, which have provided satellite imagery, drone surveillance, and training (Falode & Faseke, 2023: 1323). The U.S. Africa Command (AFRICOM) has played a vital role in enhancing Nigeria's IMINT capabilities, particularly through the deployment of drones that have been instrumental in monitoring Boko Haram's activities in remote regions like the Sambisa Forest (Oyewole, 2022). Similarly, in Somalia, IMINT operations are heavily supported by AFRICOM and other Western allies, with drones and satellite imagery being key tools in tracking al-Shabaab's movements and targeting its leadership (Kheyre, 2022). However, the extent of this support is generally more pronounced in Somalia, where the United States has conducted numerous drone strikes and provided continuous surveillance to assist both Somali forces and the African Union Mission in Somalia (AMISOM). The more extensive use of drones in Somalia reflects the greater reliance on international military assistance in a country with less developed domestic capabilities compared to Nigeria.

Additionally, the operational environments in Nigeria and Somalia present distinct challenges that impact the use of IMINT. In Nigeria, Boko Haram operates primarily in the northeastern regions, including the vast Sambisa Forest and the Lake Chad Basin, which are difficult to access and monitor. The dense vegetation and rugged terrain can obscure satellite imagery and limit the effectiveness of aerial surveillance, making it challenging to detect Boko Haram's movements and hideouts (Oyewole, 2022). Conversely, Somalia's terrain is characterized by arid and semi-arid landscapes, with al-Shabaab often operating in remote rural areas as well as blending into urban environments. The open terrain of southern Somalia can sometimes make it easier to track movements and identify targets using IMINT, though

al-Shabaab's tactic of integrating into civilian populations adds complexity to targeting operations (Ingiriis, 2020: 140). Despite these differences, in both countries, the challenging terrain requires a combination of IMINT with other intelligence methods to achieve comprehensive situational awareness.

Furthermore, the tactical application of IMINT in counterterrorism operations also shows both similarities and differences between Nigeria and Somalia. In Nigeria, IMINT has been effectively used to identify Boko Haram's camps, track convoys, and plan airstrikes, particularly in operations aimed at disrupting the group's logistical networks and rescuing hostages. The Nigerian military's use of IMINT has been crucial in several high-profile operations, such as the rescue of kidnapped Chibok schoolgirls. However, the effectiveness of these efforts is sometimes limited by the intermittent availability of IMINT assets and challenges in integrating this intelligence into broader military strategies (Falode & Faseke, 2023: 1331). In Somalia, IMINT has been used to a similar effect, providing critical intelligence for airstrikes and ground operations against al-Shabaab. The real-time surveillance provided by drones has been particularly effective in targeting al-Shabaab's leadership and monitoring the group's movements across the border with Kenya. IMINT has also been vital in supporting AMISOM's efforts to reclaim territory from al-Shabaab and disrupt its operations (Ingiriis, 2020). The constant surveillance capabilities offered by international partners in Somalia have enabled more sustained and coordinated military efforts compared to Nigeria, where IMINT resources are more sporadically deployed.

Finally, in both Nigeria and Somalia, the integration of IMINT into broader intelligence strategies is crucial for effective counterterrorism. In Nigeria, IMINT is combined with HUMINT and signals intelligence (SIGINT) to build a comprehensive understanding of Boko Haram's operations (Falode & Faseke, 2023: 1331). This multi-source intelligence approach allows for more

effective planning and execution of military operations, although challenges in coordination and information sharing can sometimes hinder its effectiveness. In Somalia, the integration of IMINT with other intelligence forms is more advanced, particularly due to the extensive involvement of international partners. AMISOM, Somali forces, and international intelligence agencies work together to pool resources and intelligence, leading to more coordinated and effective counterterrorism efforts (Kheyre, 2022). The high level of international cooperation in Somalia has facilitated the development of a more sophisticated intelligence network that is better able to respond to the dynamic threat posed by al-Shabaab.

Conclusion

This study has examined the role of IMINT in contemporary counterterrorism strategies against Boko Haram in Nigeria and Al-Shabaab in Somalia. The analysis shows that imagery-based intelligence is an important tool in modern military operations, particularly in environments where insurgents operate in remote or difficult terrain. By providing visual information through satellites, aerial reconnaissance, and unmanned aerial systems, IMINT has enhanced the ability of security forces to detect militant camps, monitor movements, and conduct more targeted operations. In both Nigeria and Somalia, such capabilities have supported efforts to disrupt insurgent networks and weaken their operational capacity.

The study also demonstrated that the effectiveness of IMINT is determined by other related conditions. In Nigeria, although aerial assets and surveillance platforms have contributed to counterterrorism efforts, their use has often been limited by technological constraints, insufficient analytical capacity, and gaps in intelligence coordination. In Somalia, by contrast, the application of IMINT has been more sustained, largely because of extensive international support and the involvement of external actors in surveillance and strike operations. These differences

highlight the importance of technological resources, trained personnel, and effective intelligence-sharing mechanisms in determining how successfully imagery intelligence can be deployed in counterinsurgency campaigns.

Nevertheless, the findings suggest that IMINT alone cannot provide a complete solution to the challenges posed by insurgent movements. Groups such as Boko Haram and Al-Shabaab have adapted their tactics in ways that reduce their visibility to aerial surveillance, including operating in small mobile units, blending into civilian populations, and exploiting natural cover. For this reason, imagery intelligence is most effective when integrated with other forms of intelligence. A multi-source intelligence framework allows analysts to validate information and produce more reliable assessments of insurgent activities. Ultimately, for countries battling insurgencies like Nigeria and Somalia, the real challenge is not only about acquiring these technologies but also how they develop the institutional capacity required to use them effectively. This requires strengthening expertise, improving coordination among intelligence agencies, and expanding international partnerships.

R E F E R E N C E S

- ABC News. (2014,). Top Al-Shabaab leader killed in airstrike, Pentagon confirms. ABC News. Sept. 5. <https://abcnews.go.com/International/top-al-shabab-leader-killed-airstrike-pentagon-confirms/story?id=25265232>
- Agbiboa, D. (2015). Resistance to Boko Haram: Civilian Joint Task Forces in north-east Nigeria. *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, Special Issue, 3–22.
- Akinbile, I. O., Chaku, S. E., Habiba, M. & Kulugh, V. E. (2025). Interrogating the effectiveness of Nigerian military cyber warfare technologies in curbing Boko Haram's cyber propaganda in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of African Studies*.
- Amaraegbu, D. A. (2013). Failure of human intelligence, Boko Haram and terrorism in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 15(4).

- Council on Foreign Relations. (2025, September 15). Conflict with al-Shabaab in Somalia. Global Conflict Tracker. <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/al-shabab-somalia>
- Dokman Tomislav. (2019) Defining the Term ‘Intelligence’ – Insight into existing Intelligence Knowledge. *Informatologia*, 52(3-4). <https://hrcak.srce.hr/file/341342>
- Egbejule, E. (2025, November 10). Terrorist turf war battle in north-eastern Nigeria leaves about 200 dead. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2025/nov/10/terrorist-turf-war-battle-north-eastern-nigeria>
- Falode, A. J. (2016). The Nature of Nigeria’s Boko Haram War, 2010-2015: A Strategic Analysis. *Perspectives on Terrorism*, 10(1), 41-52.
- Falode, A. J. (2021). Found: A Definition of Intelligence. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(1), 70-73. [https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2021.4\(1\).09](https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2021.4(1).09)
- Falode, A. & Faseke, B. O. (2023). The art of the impossible: Intelligence and Nigeria’s Boko Haram war, 2010–2021. *International Journal of Intelligence and Counterintelligence*, 36(4), 1319–1336.
- Faseke, Babajimi O. (2022). ‘National Intelligence Agency and Nigeria’s Development in the 21st Century’ in Olufunke Adeboye et al., (eds.), *Africa and the Challenge of Underdevelopment: A Festschrift in Honour of Professor Akinjide Osuntokun* (Ede: Redeemer’s University Press).
- Ingiiriis, M. H. (2020). Insurgency and international extraversion in Somalia: The National Intelligence and Security Agency (NISA) and Al-Shabaab’s Amniyat. *African Security Review*, 29(2), 125–151.
- Jensen, C., McElreath, D. & Graves, M. (2013). *Introduction to intelligence studies*. Routledge.
- Johnson, L. K. (2010). *National security intelligence: Secret operations in defense of the democracies*. Polity Press.
- Kheyre, Z. (2022). The evolution of the Al-Shabaab jihadist intelligence structure. *Intelligence and National Security*, 37, 1061–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02684527.2022.2095599>
- Lasisi, R. & Ene, R. W. (2019). Intelligence failure and insecurity in Nigeria: An analysis of the Boko Haram insurgency. *International Journal of Strategic Research in Education, Technology and Humanities*, 7(1), 106–120.
- Lowenthal, M. M. (2017). *Intelligence: From secrets to policy* (7th ed.). CQ Press.

- Marama, N. (2014). Boko Haram misleads army, kills 300 in fresh Borno attack. *Vanguard*, May 7. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/05/boko-haram-misleads-army-kills-300-fresh-borno-attack/>
- Meservey, J. (2019, September 3). Al-Shabaab's lessons for ISIS. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/ethiopia/2016-01-24/al-shababs-lessons-isis>
- Nte, N. D. (2013). An analysis of intelligence support to security operations in Nigeria: A review of some Joint Task Force operations. *Peace and Security Review*, 5(9), 1–23.
- Oriola, T. B. (2021). Nigerian soldiers on the war against Boko Haram. *African Affairs*, 120(479), 147–175.
- Oyewole, S. (2017). Making the sky relevant to battle strategy: Counterinsurgency and the prospects of air power in Nigeria. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 40(3), 211–231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2016.1188533>
- Oyewole, S. (2020). The quest for space capabilities and military security in Africa. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10220461.2020.1782258>
- Shortland, A. (2012). *Treasure mapped: Using satellite imagery to track the developmental effects of Somali piracy* (Africa Programme Paper No. AFP PP 2012/01).
- Vanguard. (2015). Chad, Niger launch air and ground strikes against Boko Haram as troops recapture Buni Yadi. *Vanguard*, March 9. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2015/03/chad-niger-launch-air-ground-strikes-against-boko-haram-as-troops-recapture-buni-yadi/>